

INTERVIEW GUIDE ADDRESSED TO TEACHERS

Validated version

DIMENSION A. BIOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION

- a.1. Could you briefly describe your academic background and professional experience?
- a.2. What functions and position do you currently hold at the school?
- a.3. Have you worked in other schools? If so, what functions and positions have you held?
- a.4. Are you, or have you ever been, responsible for the school library? If so, how would you describe your experience in that role, and what challenges or satisfactions has it brought you?
- a.5. How long have you been working in the field of education?

DIMENSION B. VIEWS ON MULTIMODAL READING AND THE SCHOOL LIBRARY

- b.1. What do you understand by reading in general? And by multimodal reading in particular?
- b.2. Do you think that images, visual sequencing, and design, in any type of medium, influence students' reading comprehension? Why?
- b.3. As a teacher, do you think there is a relationship between enjoyment of reading and reading competence? If so, how would you explain that relationship?
- b.4. Have you noticed changes in literary education and in the way reading has been promoted in recent years? If so, what changes, and why do you think they have taken place?
- b.5. Do you encounter obstacles when trying to foster students' enjoyment of reading? If so, what are they, and why?
- b.6. What types of texts are read throughout the school day? And during the half-hour reading time* in the classroom? Who selects them? If you select them yourself, what aspects do you take into account?
- b.7. How do you use the school library?
- b.8. How do students use the school library? In the case of borrowing, do they borrow comics? And picturebooks?
- b.9. From your experience, how does the school library contribute to fostering multimodal reading, that is, reading that integrates different modes (visual, verbal, digital)?
- b.10. Do you perceive resistance or prejudice toward multimodal reading on the part of teachers, students, families, or educational institutions? If so, of what kind? What do you think explains it?

DIMENSION C. KNOWLEDGE OF PICTUREBOOKS AND COMICS

- c.1. Have you received training in children's and young adult literature? If so, what kind?
- c.2. Have you received specific training in multimodal reading? If so, what kind?

c.3. Have you received specific training in picturebooks? If so, what kind? And in comics? If so, what kind?

c.4. What characteristics do you consider most relevant in a good picturebook for reading mediation in the classroom? And in a comic?

c.5. Are there any authors, illustrators, publishers, or series that you find especially interesting or consider to be points of reference in picturebooks? If so, which ones? And in comics? If so, which ones?

c.6. Do you usually discover new picturebook publications? If so, how? And comics? If so, how?

c.7. Do you think reading picturebooks provides benefits? And limitations? If so, which ones?

c.8. Do you think reading comics provides benefits? And limitations? If so, which ones?

DIMENSION D. PICTUREBOOK AND COMIC COLLECTION

d.1. How do you assess the picturebook collection in the school library? And in the classroom library?

d.2. How do you assess the comic collection in the school library? And in the classroom library?

d.3. How do you assess the quality of the editions of the picturebooks in the school library collection? And in the classroom library? And the comics?

d.4. How do primary school students usually respond to this type of multimodal reading? Could you mention any specific experience?

d.5. At your school, what criteria are taken into account when selecting or recommending picturebooks and comics to students? And in your own teaching practice, do you use any personal criteria? If so, which ones?

d.6. How do you organize your classroom library collection in primary education? Is there coordination with the school library?

d.7. Do you think that the school library collection, in terms of comics and picturebooks, responds to the interests and motivations of today's students? If so, why? And the classroom library collection? If so, why?

d.8. What resources or funding channels (provided by the school, the educational administration, or external programs) does the school have to promote activities or projects related to picturebooks or comics in the school setting?

DIMENSION E. READING AND MEDIATION PRACTICES

e.1. As a teacher, could you describe a specific experience that you consider significant or successful in promoting reading?

e.2. Do you incorporate picturebooks into your reading activities or projects? If so, in what way? And comics? If so, in what way?

e.3. Do you encounter difficulties in including picturebooks and comics in curricular planning? If so, what are they? (budget, space, training, institutional support, etc.)

DIMENSION F. INTERINSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATION FOR THE PROMOTION OF MULTIMODAL READING

f.1. Are there any joint projects or activities between your school and other institutions (libraries, the university, associations, publishers, or local bodies) aimed at promoting reading? If so, which ones?

f.2. What strategies or resources are used at the school to promote multimodal reading (workshops, fairs, exhibitions, etc.)? If they are not used, how do you think it could be promoted?

f.3. Are digital resources or social media used to disseminate or support the school's reading activities? If so, what dissemination do they have, and what is their reach?

f.4. What relationship exists, or should exist, between your school and the library in order to promote multimodal reading?

f.5. What collaborations or synergies would you like to strengthen in order to reinforce reading mediation and reading promotion in your school environment?

DIMENSION G. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES ON READING

g.1. How do you imagine reading in the coming years in relation to multimodality and new reading formats (apps, video games, social media)?

g.2. If you could propose a specific improvement or initiative for reading promotion at your school that incorporated graphic narratives, what would it be and why?

g.3. What role do you think the school plays, or should play, in the formation of multimodal and critical readers in the 21st century?

INTERVIEW GUIDE ADDRESSED TO LIBRARIANS

Validated version

DIMENSION A. BIOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION

- a.1. Could you briefly describe your academic background and professional experience?
- a.2. What functions and position do you currently hold in the library?
- a.3. Have you worked in other libraries? If so, what functions and positions have you held?
- a.4. How long have you been working in the library field?

DIMENSION B. VIEWS ON MULTIMODAL READING AND THE PUBLIC LIBRARY

- b.1. What do you understand by reading in general? And by multimodal reading in particular?
- b.2. Do you think that images, visual sequencing, and design, in any type of medium, influence the reading comprehension of child users? Why? And in the case of young adult users, why?
- b.3. From your experience, how does the public library contribute to fostering multimodal reading, that is, reading that integrates different modes (visual, verbal, digital)?
- b.4. Do you perceive resistance or prejudice toward multimodal reading on the part of other librarians, users, families, or other cultural institutions? If so, of what kind? What do you think explains it?
- b.5. Approximately, what volume of child users does the library usually have (for example, per month or per year)? And of young adult users? In relation to the usual number of users, what percentage do child users represent? And young adult users?
- b.6. In your view, what are the main challenges libraries face today in fostering enjoyment of reading?
- b.7. As a librarian, do you think there is a relationship between enjoyment of reading and reading competence? If so, how would you explain that relationship?

DIMENSION C. KNOWLEDGE OF PICTUREBOOKS AND COMICS

- c.1. Have you received training in children's and young adult literature? If so, what kind?
- c.2. Have you received specific training in multimodal reading? If so, what kind?
- c.3. Have you received specific training in picturebooks? If so, what kind? And in comics? If so, what kind?
- c.4. What characteristics do you consider most relevant in a good picturebook? And in a comic?
- c.5. Are there any authors, illustrators, publishers, or series that you find especially interesting or consider to be points of reference in picturebooks? If so, which ones? And in comics? If so, which ones?
- c.6. Do you usually discover new picturebook publications? If so, how? And comics? If so, how?

c.7. Do you think reading picturebooks provides benefits? And limitations? If so, which ones?

c.8. Do you think reading comics provides benefits? And limitations? If so, which ones?

DIMENSION D. PICTUREBOOK AND COMIC COLLECTION

d.1. How do you assess the picturebook collection in the library's children's and young adult section?

d.2. How do you assess the comic collection in the library's children's and young adult section?

d.3. In the library, has the presence of these multimodal readings changed in recent years in terms of quantity, variety, or visibility?

d.4. How do you assess the quality of the editions of the picturebooks in the library collection? And the comics?

d.5. What criteria are used for the selection, acquisition, or renewal of these multimodal readings? Have these criteria changed over time?

d.6. Who is involved in these decisions regarding selection, acquisition, or renewal?

d.7. How are picturebooks physically organized in the library? And comics?

d.8. Do you consider that the library's current collection responds to the interests of child users? Why? And of young adult users? Why?

d.9. What do you observe regarding the level of demand for or borrowing of the library collection by child users? And by young adult users?

d.10. What institutional support or funding channels exist to maintain or expand this collection?

DIMENSION E. READING AND MEDIATION PRACTICES

e.1. Could you mention any significant reading mediation experience that has been well received by the library's users?

e.2. What is done in the library to give visibility to and encourage the use of picturebooks and comics?

e.3. What improvements would you propose to enhance the visibility and use of these multimodal readings in the library?

e.4. In what way are picturebooks incorporated into reading mediation activities in the library? And comics?

e.5. Do you encounter difficulties in promoting picturebooks and comics in the library? If so, what are they? (budget, space, training, institutional support, etc.)

DIMENSION F. INTERINSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATION FOR THE PROMOTION OF MULTIMODAL READING

f.1. Are there any joint projects or activities between the library where you work and other institutions (schools, the university, associations, publishers, or local bodies) aimed at promoting reading? If so, which ones?

f.2. What strategies or resources are used in the library to promote multimodal reading (workshops, fairs, exhibitions, etc.)? If they are not used, how do you think it could be promoted? And in the case of digital reading, if it is not being promoted, how do you think it could be encouraged?

f.3. In addition to access to the catalogue, does the library have digital reading rooms or devices?

f.4. Are digital resources or social media used to disseminate or support the library's reading activities? If so, what dissemination do they have, and what is their reach?

f.5. What relationship exists, or should exist, between the library and schools in order to promote multimodal reading?

f.6. What collaborations or synergies would you like to strengthen in order to reinforce reading mediation and reading promotion in the library environment?

DIMENSION G. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES ON READING

g.1. How do you imagine reading in the coming years in relation to multimodality and new visual or digital formats (apps, video games, social media)?

g.2. If you could propose a specific improvement or initiative for promoting multimodal reading in the library where you work, what would it be and why?

g.3. What role do you think the public library plays, or should play, in the formation of multimodal and critical readers in the 21st century?